

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D11.1 – Data Management Plan

WP11 – Project Management
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Executive Summary

EOSC-Life will make LS RIs data resources FAIR and publish them in the EOSC following guidelines and standards (e.g. EDML). Overall this will drive the evolution of the RI repository infrastructure for EOSC and integration of the LS RI repositories. EOSC-Life will implement workflows that cross disciplines and RI boundaries and address the needs of interdisciplinary science. The goal of the EOSC-Life project is to make sure that life-scientists can find, access and integrate life-science data for analysis and reuse in academic and industrial research. EOSC-Life will transform European life-science by providing an open, continent-scale, collaborative and interdisciplinary environment for data-driven life science. This requires a knowledge management plan (i.e., data management + knowledge environment management) that covers aspects of the different activities to build up for the platform that cater to the EOSC-Life mission. This document, though titled Data Management Plan, therefore, will also include the aspects of managing software tools, compute cloud architectures, and interoperability of these components as the foundation for the EOSC-Life knowledge environment. Additionally, EOSC-Life data management plan will address the data policies needed for human research data under GDPR. Interoperable provenance information describes the history of sample and data to ensure reproducibility and adherence to regulatory requirements.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed to the following project objectives:

- a. Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources for cloud use
- b. Create an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC
- c. Enable ground-breaking data driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC

D11.1 lays out the foundational guidelines in a data management plan to effectively bring together the 13 Biological and Medical ESFRI research infrastructures (LS RIs). This will contribute to the creation of an open collaborative space for digital biology. D11.1 builds on extensive previous collaborative work between the European LS RI¹.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/record/154022>, <https://zenodo.org/record/376236>, <https://zenodo.org/record/1441303>, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3238496>, <https://zenodo.org/record/1408804#.W5JVnyAyWUk>

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

1. Introduction

As a major funder of research and infrastructure, the European Commission has a clear commitment to open science highlighted in the 2019 publication on Open science, Open Data, and Open Scholarship². These principles are reflected in its Horizon 2020 2018-2020 Work programme (Section 16 - Science with and for society)³. As the representatives of Research Infrastructures that have been established to support the ecosystem of modern collaborative science, the EOSC-Life participants are fully committed to this ethos and are actively working towards the same agenda.

As a large and highly distributed project, it is essential that the EOSC-Life consortium establish robust working practices that will maximise the value of the project's outcomes. As part of this goal, the consortium is committed to enact effective data management policies both to safeguard data with compliances to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁴ and other national regulations during the project, and to ensure responsible stewardship following its conclusion. This applies not only to any experimental research data generated by funded activities, but also to the tools and knowledge we expect to generate. In so doing, the consortium can maximise the utility of the project's deliverables in the communities of the participating Research Infrastructures, and thus maximise the return on the Commission's investment.

All of the Research Infrastructures participating in EOSC-Life take central roles in the provision of infrastructure to safeguard data for their respective scientific communities - facilitating access, reuse, and reproducibility. Key to this is not only to ensure that research data and tools are made available, but that they can be shared in such a way as to help researchers make use of them interoperably and seamlessly with the capacity building that supports the reuse and sharing of these resources. These requirements are exemplified in the FAIR Principles - that resources (data, analytic softwares, compute infrastructures) are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable⁵. The recommendation of FAIR implementation is also recognised in the 2018 publication on "Turning FAIR into Reality" by the European Commission⁶. Improving the infrastructure that allows scientists to make research data and process conform to these guiding principles are a key aim to the EOSC-Life remit, including the management of data and tools across infrastructure boundaries.

²https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337863024_Open_Science_Open_Data_and_Open_Scholarship_European_Policies_to_Make_Science_Fit_for_the_Twenty-First_Century

³https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2018-2020/main/h2020-wp1820-swfs_en.pdf

⁴<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>

⁵<https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>, <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

⁶https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf

2. General Approach

As a cluster of Research Infrastructures, the EOSC-Life's approach to ensuring effective data management and stewardship relies upon the existing policies and expertise of the infrastructures. The Research Infrastructures have established data strategies appropriate to the type of data and tools and - having the relevant expertise - are best placed to implement those strategies⁷.

Additionally, the GDPR will be implemented accordingly to meet the legal and technical requirements for the realisation of EOSC. Where appropriate and required, personal, confidential, and private data will be redacted at the source of contribution prior to feeding into the knowledge sharing platform. In the federated setting of distributed research infrastructures, best practices have been identified and shall be exploited as recommended by strategy and implementation experts.

Common across these strategies is a commitment to open science, pursuing the goal of sharing the outputs of publicly funded research whilst respecting the varying ethical and legal contexts of these outputs and taking account of the technical and social challenges of knowledge sharing via reusing of data, tool softwares, and high-performance computing infrastructures. For example, the majority of the data, interoperability tools, software, and hardware resources managed by ELIXIR are routinely made available openly. Similarly the INSTRUCT community has a long-standing tradition of depositing data in established domain archives as a matter of practice. Euro-Bioimaging is specifically seeking to encourage a similar ethos of data sharing by developing standards and technical solutions, by addressing data flow in tandem with access to the imaging infrastructure, as well as the identification of reference datasets. On the other hand, sharing of data and resources in BBMRI or ECRIN requires a specialised approach due to the sensitive nature of the data. The Research Infrastructures are working to improve access to human research data through technical solutions for managed access. This includes secure computational infrastructure for specific individuals to access data consented for research, but also exposing metadata to allow discovery⁸.

Within EOSC-Life, the handling and deposition of research outputs will not be managed centrally. Instead, responsibility is delegated to the Research Infrastructures, who will retain control over and accountability for each dataset, service, publication and software tool produced in the context of EOSC-Life. By adopting this strategy, EOSC-Life can better ensure efficient and effective management to also comply with the legal requirements such as GDPR by clearly and unambiguously assigning responsibility for the project's outputs to the investigators producing them. This allows the project to leverage the significant data management expertise of the partners implementing each task. During the project lifetime, the data management plan will be reviewed and updated periodically to reflect interoperability, appropriate safeguards and best

⁷ <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8304>, <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16413>

⁸ Drysdale, R. et al. *Bioinformatics* 36, 2636–2642 (2020), Saunders, G. et al. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 20, 1–9 (2019)., Holub et al.: <https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2017.0110>, Ohmann, C. et al. *BMJ Open* 7, e018647–25 (2017).

practices recommended by experts in the other EC-funded projects that are emerging as specialists of FAIR knowledge management⁹.

The knowledge and data management within EOSC-Life informs and is informed by development in the wider EOSC ecosystem such as EOSC-wide working groups on sustainability and FAIR data¹⁰. For instance, the EOSCPilot project developed the EOSC Dataset Minimal Information model (EDMI)¹¹ that steers the use of Bioschemas¹² within EOSC-Life.

3. Data

Many of the Research Infrastructures participating in EOSC-Life such as BBMRI, ELIXIR, ECRIN and EATRIS fulfil key roles in managing access to (aggregated) scientific data or metadata, with varying approaches to data sharing as appropriate. EOSC-Life is thus part of the effort to build Europe's data management and data stewardship infrastructure, and this is reflected in its tasks and deliverables. In WP4, BBMRI, EATRIS, and ECRIN will lead the deliverables surrounding guidelines and requirements of sharing of sensitive data, regulatory compliance, identifying standards, tools, and the registries to facilitate sharing and reuse of multimodal data, and the data standards for observational and interventional studies and on the interoperability between healthcare and research data (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3, D4.4, and D4.5).

It is essential to note that data management and data sharing infrastructure in itself relies upon the FAIR principles to effectively connect up the federated knowledge and expertise within the EOSC landscape. WP6 (led by INSERM and BBMRI) will establish the FAIR requirement document (D6.1¹³), and the data provenance model (D6.2 and D6.6) that act as a basis for implementation of tooling and registries of data resources and standards (D6.3, D6.4, D6.5). Interoperability of data (and tools) is the key driver of EOSC-Life, and work done in WP6 will deliver standards and schemas guidelines that will address issues such as cross-domain identifiers use and provenance.

4. Tools and Infrastructures

In addition to data, software tools and compute cloud infrastructure are essential components in the EOSC-Life Open Science framework. This requires careful management and stewardship. Provision of core infrastructure for interoperability is a key component that is a shared responsibility between WP2 (Tools Collaboratory), WP5 (User management and access services), and WP7 (Cloud deployment services) that are guided by principle studies in WP1 for cloud feasibility (D1.1), and EOSC sustainability best practice that is to be concluded in D1.4. Examples of services that will be developed in EOSC-Life include those for EOSC FAIR services deployment

⁹ e.g. <https://fairplus-project.eu/>, <https://b1mg-project.eu/>, <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>, <https://www.fair4health.eu/>, [ELIXIR-CONVERGE](#), etc

¹⁰ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/fair-working-group>, <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/sites/default/files/eosc-interoperability-framework-v1.0.pdf>

¹¹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/edmi-metadata-guidelines>,

¹² <https://bioschemas.org/>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3693883>

and registries, cloud implementation of exemplary workflows, and EDMI-compliance interoperability services in the cloud. Ultimately, tools and infrastructure implementation and guidelines will feed into the Common Framework for quality, data, and service management and the reproducibility analysis in WP8 (D8.2 and D8.4).

Access to tools and data that are stored in the cloud requires secure connections equipped with a robust and stringent authentication to ensure that only strictly the right authority can access the right data. Masaryk University (MU) and INSTRUCT are developing an access and user management system for life science authentication and authorisation interface (LS-AAI - the blueprint, D5.1¹⁴) in WP5 (User management and access services). EDMI compliance and cloud feasibility studies of software and data in WP1 will also guide the delivery of the EOSC-LS observatory report in WP7. The EOSC sustainability and research reproducibility is pending on the principle of open science. Findings and deliverables of WP1, WP2, WP7, WP8 will contribute to the EOSC sustainability and reproducibility framework to establish policies and/or recommendations around open development and open source. This provides a powerful mechanism not only to disseminate the results of publicly funded software development, but also a major driver of software quality. A strong adoption of open source already exists within the biomedical science community¹⁵, but as with data, the approach of research infrastructures and EOSC-Life must respect the commercial and operational context of the participants.

5. Knowledge and capability-capacity building

An accommodating framework that allows knowledge dissemination and capability & capacity building is an underlying prerequisite for sustainability of EOSC-Life. Such a framework should aim to include the aspect of research reproducibility to contribute to the goal of achieving project sustainability. WP8 (International impact, innovation and sustainability) will deliver the framework to assess reproducibility (D8.1), while WP9 (Training of the EOSC-Life community) will serve the function of building capability and capacity for the uptake of EOSC-Life resources to build the user base for the community. Gap analysis of the training needs (D9.1¹⁶, D9.2) will address areas for training implementation and the training activities' impact (D9.3). This will also contribute to the strategy to engage with key stakeholders to be identified by WP10 (Dissemination and outreach - D10.1, D10.2) which, in turn, will be essential for the sustainability of the project

Wherever appropriate, EOSC-Life deliverables will be published in an open fashion and deposited in repositories such as OpenAIRE-Zenodo to support FAIR consumption of the EOSC-Life services and products. Likewise, peer-reviewed articles will be published under open-access terms. The project will also result in the production of guidelines, standards, and other best-practices documents, which will also be published openly. Partners retained responsibility for choosing the appropriate publication channel (e.g., the journal), but infrastructures can implement mechanisms to facilitate the publication process. For example, ELIXIR has established a gateway

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3386307>

¹⁵ Jiménez RC, et al. Four simple recommendations to encourage best practices in research software <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11407.1>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3692068>

within the F1000 Research¹⁷, using the post-publication transparent review process for peer-reviewed articles, and channels for other types of publications such as reports, posters, and slide sets.

6. Processing of personal data under GDPR

The European Life Science Research Infrastructures will all have to process personal data in some form - ranging from e.g. names, affiliations and emails in service applications to managing and providing access to aggregated research data (e.g. genomes, biomarkers and imaging data from human research participants).

The final responsibility for the lawful processing of data sits with the data collecting and/or processing project participant (EOSC-Life Consortium Agreement Art 4.5/4.6):

4.5 Compliance

Each Party shall ensure that its work on the Project complies fully with all applicable national and international laws, regulations and guidelines which are effective during the period of this Agreement and the Grant Agreement, including those governing health and safety, data protection, and where relevant, the use of human or animal subjects and good clinical practice. In this regard, each Party shall maintain the confidentiality, in accordance with this Consortium Agreement, of all samples and data relating to the use of human subjects, which is created or used in the course of the Project.

4.6 Data Protection

The Parties must Process Personal Data within the Project, required for performing the Action in compliance with Data Protection Legislation. Each Party represents and warrants that they will Process and transport and subsequent dispose of Personal Data required for use in the Project or generated during the Project in compliance with Data Protection Legislation (including, without being limited to, concluding additional contracts, authorisation or notification requirements and where applicable local ethical guidelines). Furthermore, each Party represents and warrants that any ethics committee approvals and Data Subject informed consents or other requirements – in so far needed under applicable Data Protection Legislation – required for performing the Action will be obtained or established prior to the commencement of the respective part of the Allocated Work. The Parties may grant their personnel access only to such Personal Data if this is strictly necessary for implementing, performing, managing and monitoring the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement.

In EOSC-Life WP4 has a central role in facilitating the data processing for the project beneficiaries (and ultimately the life science users of the LS RI services). In the CORBEL project the BBMRI ELSI Knowledge Base and Helpdesk¹⁸ was expanded to help not only biobankers but also researchers from and users of the LS Research Infrastructures community with practical questions related to ethical, legal and societal issues that may arise in the context of a project or task¹⁹. In EOSC-Life these services will be further developed in WP4 (e.g. D4.2 " Report on requirements for regulatory

¹⁷ <http://f1000research.com/channels/elixir>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2018.0018>

¹⁹ CORBEL D7.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3859795>

compliance of sensitive health data and biological and medical research data management²⁰). For instance, requirements for compliant processing of personal data in cloud environments will be clarified and used to guide implementation of cloud services (D4.1 Requirements for hosting/distributing and access control for sensitive data). Project management together with WP4 will provide the oversight mechanism via regular activity reports (WP12 reports).

Consequently, this means all parties are responsible for their own adherence to EU but also local laws and regulations, including the demonstration of compliance.

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed:

Yes

The delivery was delayed for a period of 12 months due to the decision to include the Ethics deliverables as part of the data management. The SEAB met the first time at the AGM at the beginning of March, but then work was further delayed because of urgent COVID-19 related activities.

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3820389>

